

THE USE OF SERIAL IMAGE FOR IMPROVING DEAF CHILDREN' EXPRESSIVE WRITING SKILL IN CLASS IV OF SLB DHARMA BHAKTI, BANTUL, INDONESIA 2018/2019

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Abstract:

The purpose of the current study was to improve the deaf students' expressive writing skill in class IV SLB Dharma Bhakti Bantul by using the serial picture. This study was classified into Classroom Action Research. The primary data of the study were the process description and the students' learning outcome. The primary data were supported by the observation result. The results of the study were analyzed by using descriptive qualitative analysis. The data were collected by using: 1) observation, 2) test, 3) interview. The result of the study showed that serial picture could be used to improve the deaf students' expressive writing skill in class IV of SLB Dharma Bhakti Bantul. This was shown by the students' improvement of expressive writing skill from cycle I and II. There was significant improvement by achieving minimum mastery criteria of 60.

Keywords: serial picture, expressive writing, deaf children

1. Introduction

Writing is one of the language skills that can be separated from reading, speaking, and listening. In learning expressive writing for deaf children, these four language skills should obtain equal and integrated portion. Accordingly, writing should be integrated with reading, listening, and speaking.

Moreover, for deaf children, expressive writing is the highest language ability because, in this activity, the deaf children learn to imagine and to think in abstract according to their thinking level.

Expressive writing is the highest level of communicative ability. It is the final level of writing ability. Anyaswati (Henry Guntur, 2005: 10) argues that writing is a mean of communication an individual needs to develop their self-potential or to interact with their surroundings.

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Expressive writing ability is built upon previous language mastery, namely, listening ability, reading ability, and speaking ability. Once the children master those aspects, the next step is to teach children writing letters, from small letters until capital letters (Nursisto 2000: 5).

Regarding expressive writing, it was found that in SLB Dharma Bhakti Bantul, many deaf children had not mastered the basic ability of expressive writing. Some of the obstacles faced by the children in learning expressive writing were difficulty in determining appropriate word choice, sentence and spelling mastery, and difficulty in understanding a sound symbol in the form of a word.

Deaf children' limited development makes the lack of ability in developing the idea. Their hearing function makes them find difficulty in capturing the word they listen, which affects their writing. Their poor concentration in reading lip affects their ability in writing the stated word. They tended to write words they spelled out.

In SLB Dharma Bhakti Bantul, the portion for expressive writing was still minimum. The students held small chances to apply it into real work.

In order to overcome the problems faced by the deaf children in writing, various attempts shall be made, various alternative, both strategy and media, should be tried out to make students are able to capture the spoken language and translate it into a learning activity that can improve their expressive wiring skill. Accordingly, one of the attempts is by using the serial picture as a learning media by using a picture. The use of serial picture aims to students' writing skill so that they can absorb as many information as possible. By seeing pictures, the child will find it easier to think in a semi-concrete way so that the children find it easier to express their thought into writing.

The serial picture was selected as a learning media for expressive writing skill because it is easy-to-make and easy-to-use. Seeing the serial picture becomes one of the inputs that stimulate deaf children expressing their feeling, idea, or thought into a written form. By the use of the serial picture, the children are trained to use their sense, namely visual and hearing sense for children with mild hearing loss (R. Angkowo and A. Kosasih, 2007: 28).

It is expected that by using serial picture, the children will be easier to focus so that they can develop their interest and be stimulated in expressing an idea in a written form. The picture of activity sequence or criteria is presented consecutively. It trains children to discover phenomena and activity.

Based on the background of the problem and problem identification, the problem of the study was stated as: how to improve the deaf students' expressive writing skill in class IV SLB Dharma Bhakti Bantul by using the serial picture.

2. Research Method

This was categorized as Classroom Action Research. This study was conducted in deaf students of class IV SDLB in SLB Dharma Bhakti Bantul. Two deaf students were

selected as the sample of the study. This study was conducted in semester II of the academic year of 2018/2019 for three months.

The subject of the study, according to Suharsimi Arikunto (2005: 99), refers to a material, condition, or an individual where the data and problems are attached to. The subjects were one female and one male student. The design of the present study was the model developed by Hopkins (Suhadjono, 2006:105). The instrument validity test was done by consultation with the academic advisor, school principal, and teachers.

The data were analyzed qualitatively. The data were in the form of information or phenomena. They were compared to analyze the data and facts to generate a conclusion. It was done by analyzing the word or the sentence so that a clear conclusion can be drawn.

3. Result and Discussion

The result of the study showed that there is an improvement in deaf children' expressive writing skill after participated in learning activity using serial pictures. This could be seen from the learning activity and the result of score comparison of each student.

Table 10: The Comparison of students' expressive writing skill score before the treatment, after treatment I, and after treatment II

No.	Subject	Before the treatment		After the treatment Treatment I		Improvement	After the treatment Treatment II		Improvement
		Score	Criteria	Score	Criteria		Score	Criteria	
1.	Fiy	40	Very low	47	Low	7	70	Fair	23
2.	Ay	26	Very low	45	Low	20	62	Fair	17

From the table above, it was clear that there was an improvement over time. It can be seen in the following figure.

Figure 3: Expressive writing skill before treatment, after the treatment I, and after the treatment II

Based on the table and graphic, the description is as follow:

- By using the serial picture as the primary media for expressive learning, there was a significant improvement in each stage. Fiy's expressive writing skill before the treatment was 40 and was categorized as very low, after the treatment I, Fiy's score was 47 and was categorized as low, after treatment II, the score improved to 70 and was categorized as fair (above the minimum mastery criteria).
- After using serial picture in expressive writing subject, there was an improvement from Ay, before the treatment, Ay's score was 26 and was categorized as very low and 45 after treatment I and was categorized as low, then become 62 and was categorized as fair. (above the minimum mastery criteria).

4. Conclusion

The result and the discussion conclude that serial picture could be used to improve the deaf students' expressive writing skill in class IV of SLB Dharma Bhakti Bantul. This was shown by the students' improvement of expressive writing skill from cycle I and II. There was significant improvement by achieving minimum mastery criteria of 60.

The procedure in conducting the learning process using a serial picture to improve expressive writing skill was: the teacher distributed the serial picture, and the students attempt to say the word and sentence in the picture. The teacher corrects the student before writing the word and sentence. Then, the teacher writes it in the form of essay, in accordance with the teacher's guidance. Cycle I had not gained the score above the Minimum Mastery Standard, Cycle II was conducted by using colored serial picture and papers selected by the children themselves.

4.1 Suggestion

Based on the conclusion above, the followings are the suggestion:

a. for teachers

In the expressive writing skill learning process, the teacher should use various serial pictures in order to develop students' idea so that their vocabulary increases. The teacher should continue the material that has been delivered in accordance with the present study.

b. for parents

The parents are expected to monitor the children' expressive writing skill continuously. The serial picture should also be used at home by the parents' guidance in order to create a balance between the learning activity at home and at school.

c. for students

Students should be trained more often both at school and at home. They should be more active to learn expressive writing with the surrounding environment as its theme.

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